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ASSESSING THE APPLICATION OF PASSIVE ARCHITECTURE PRINCIPLES IN FACULTIES OF AGRICULTURAL BUILDINGS IN HOT DRY CLIMATE OF NIGERIA

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Abstract

Passive Architecture seeks to improve the ventilation in buildings for optimal human comfort. This could be achieved by the incorporation of some passive architecture principles. This present study, examined the extent at which passive architectural principles have been applied in some selected Faculties of Agricultural buildings in hot dry climatic region in Nigeria. The study used a case study based approach to assess the application of the principles in the selected buildings, which were selected based on the fact that they are among the first Faculties in their respective institutions established to promote the production of agricultural products in Nigeria. The choices of the institutions were also based on fair representation of the various generations of institutions in hot dry climate of Nigeria, such as first generation, second generations and Universities of Technology. Available passive architectural principles derived from literature were used as check list for assessing the extent of application of the principles. The results indicated that some of the principles such as: building orientation, building forms and solar shading were applied to about 60% in the selected Building. However, other principles like Induced ventilation, selection of materials for construction and cooling techniques were poorly applied. In conclusion, the study advocates for holistic application of passive architectural principles for the effective performances of buildings, minimization of the use of artificial or mechanical energy and optimal satisfaction of the occupants. It is recommended that adequate emphasis should be given to evaporative cooling techniques, choice of materials for construction and induced ventilation techniques in the design of Faculty buildings in hot dry climatic regions of Nigeria. These principles were grossly lacking in the cases studied.

Keywords; Energy, Comfort, Passive Architecture, Educational Building, Case Study and Hot dry Climate

INTRODUCTION

Educational buildings such as Faculties of Agriculture are major energy consumers, due to significant demands for heating and cooling to provide thermal comfort. Students and staff spend long periods of their time in classrooms, offices and laboratories, of which a favourable indoor environment can help to optimize their performance (Khaled *et al*, 2012). Extreme heat presents special problems in urban areas because of the retention of heat by buildings in hot dry climate (Weihe, 1985). Furthermore, many

Educational buildings are not suitable for occupants because they were designed with little or no consideration for specific climatic condition. In addition, most institutions in Nigeria find it difficult in the provision of mechanical means for heating and cooling in achieving comfort and wellbeing of occupants. This is due to its capital intensive nature and epileptic public electric power supply. Therefore, passive means of achieving comfort remains the best solution among other strategies (Saliu & Achimugu, 2016).

Passive architecture is an energy conscious approach to design that seeks to provide the building's operational energy, using the local climatic conditions and without the use of any electrical or mechanical devices. Fundamentally, in hot dry climates such as Nigeria, passive architecture design strategies aim to avoid heat from the sun, promote natural cross ventilation from the prevailing wind and ensure daylight into the building (Zaki *et al.*, 2008).

Therefore, the aim of this paper is to study the application of the principles of passive Architecture in Faculties of Agricultural buildings in hot dry climate regions of Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The hot dry climatic zone of Nigeria is characterized by a period of high temperature and low relative humidity between the months of February and May. The zone is reported to have a daily mean maximum indoor temperature of 37 °C of most buildings and low indoor air velocity (Akande, 2010).

Passive Architecture (PA) is a term coined to describe buildings designed to be responsive to the local climatic conditions such that comfortable indoor condition is created naturally, for as long as possible. The terminology is expressed as 'passive' to portray a defensive or protective approach of building design in shielding occupants from the local

climate elements; and 'architecture' place this responsibility to the 'Architect' being the professional obligated to create good building design (Zaki *et al.*, 2008). Fundamentally, in hot and humid tropics such as Nigeria, PA design strategies aim to avoid heat from the sun, promote natural cross ventilation from the prevailing wind and ensure daylight into the building.

Various studies such as Zaki *et al.*, (2008), Akande (2010), Arif (2012), and Geetha & Velraj (2012) all advocated the importance of using passive architectural principles in the designing for hot-dry climatic regions. These principles involve:

- Building orientation
- Evaporative cooling
- Building form
- Solar shading
- Induced ventilation
- Building materials and construction.

Building Orientation

Thomas and Garnham (2007) noted that building orientation is a fundamental first action in making "passive" building and it should be determined by factors of the sun and the prevailing winds. According to La Roche *et al.* (2001), buildings in the tropic should avoid large fenestration on the west and east which receive approximately twice the amount of solar irradiation compared to on the north and south sides.

Figure 1: Building Orientation
Source: Zaid *et al.*, (2008).

Form of the Building

Building form has great potential to reduce building energy intensity. Certain common building shapes greatly increase envelope area to volume ratio (for example, thin high-rise towers) which can decrease building energy performance in heating dominant buildings. With a similar square footage, buildings with a smaller exterior envelope area will achieve better energy-efficient performance. A compact building shape significantly reduces the building's energy intensity and reduces the need for active mechanical systems (Mikler *et al.*, 2008).

Solar Shading

Well-designed sun control and shading devices, either as parts of a building or separately placed from a building facade, can dramatically reduce building peak heat gain and cooling requirements and improve the natural lighting quality of building interiors. Sun shading devices should be provided corresponds to the sun path. For tropical countries, the best type and position for sun shading devices according to Koch-Nielsen (2007) is projected canopy at the top of windows on the east and west; and protruding fins at the sides of windows on the north and south as indicated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Different types of shading devices
Source: Arif, (2012).

Induced Ventilation

Designing to take advantage of natural ventilation especially for night cooling is very important. A primary strategy for cooling buildings without mechanical assistance (passive cooling) in hot climates is to employ natural ventilation. Designing an efficient naturally ventilated building requires a good knowledge of the air flow patterns around it and the effect of the surrounding buildings. The objective is to ventilate the largest possible parts of the interior space. Achieving this objective depends on the window location, interior design and wind characteristics (Geetha and Velraj 2012). Other forms of ventilation techniques include air vents, solar chimneys and wind towers.

Building Materials and Construction

The selection of the appropriate building material for the building envelope also plays a very important role in achieving energy efficient building. The amount of heat gains or loss and wind that flows into the building depends on components of the building envelope. The important components of the building envelope that affect the performance of the building are: Walls, Roof, Window, and Surface finishes. A building characterized by high thermal mass will absorb and store heat as well as facilitate slow rise of internal temperature on hot days (Mikler *et al.*, 2008).

Evaporative Cooling Techniques

Evaporative cooling is a passive architecture principle in which outdoor air is cooled by evaporating water before it is introduced in the building. Its physical principle lies in the fact that the heat of air is used to evaporate water, thus cooling the air, which in turn cools the living space in the building. However

passive evaporative cooling can also be indirect. The roof could be cooled with a pond, wetted pads or spray, and the ceiling transformed into a cooling element that cools the space below by convection and radiation without raising the indoor humidity (Geetha and Velraj 2012). Passive downdraft evaporative cooling tower is another technique to achieve evaporative cooling in buildings. The system consists of a downdraft tower with wetted cellulose pads at the top of the tower. Water is distributed on the top of the pads, collected at the bottom into a sump and re-circulated by a pump (Geetha and Velraj 2012).

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a case study approach to evaluate the application of principles of passive Architecture in Faculty of Agricultural buildings in a hot dry climate in Nigeria. The cases studied were: Faculty of Agriculture, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria (A.B.U), Faculty of Agriculture, Bayero University Kano (B.U.K) and School of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology, Federal University of Technology, Minna (FUTM). The cases studied were selected based on the fact that they are among the first faculties in their respective institutions established to promote the production of agricultural products in Nigeria. The choices of their institutions was also to have a fair representation of the various generations of institutions in hot dry climate of Nigeria, such as First generation (ABU), Second generation (B.U.K) and Universities of Technology (FUTM). Checklist deduced from literature (Zaki *et al.*, 2008; Akande 2010; Arif, 2012; Geetha and Velraj 2012; Abdullahi, 2016) was used to collect data on the six principles as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Checklist for Passive Architecture Source: Authors, 2017

PASSIVE ARCHITECTURE PRINCIPLES	
Scale Factor: Excellent = 5, Very good = 4, Good = 3, Weak = 2, Very weak = 1.	
VARIABLES	SCALE FACTOR
1. BUILDING ORIENTATION	
2. BUILDING FORM	
3. SOLAR SHADING	
(a) Shading by overhangs, louvers and awnings	
(b) Shading by roof	
(c) Shading by trees and vegetation	
4. INDUCED VENTILATION TECHNIQUES	
(a) Solar Chimney	
(b) Air Vent	
(c) Wind Tower	
(d) window openings	
5. MATERIALS AND CONSTRUCTION	
(a) High thermal mass building materials	
(b) Double glazing	
(c) Cavity walls	
6. EVAPORATIVE COOLING	
(a) Passive downdraft evaporative cooling	
(b) Evaporative cooling by surrounding water body	

RESULTS:

This section presents findings on the application of the six Principles of Passive Architecture from Faculty of Agriculture Ahmadu Bello University Zaria (A.B.U), Faculty of Agriculture Bayero University Kano (B.U.K) and School of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology, Federal University of Technology, Minna (FUTM). The principles are; Building Orientation, Building Form, Solar Shading, Induced Ventilation Techniques, Materials and Construction and Evaporative Cooling as illustrated in Table 1

Building Orientation

Most of the buildings within the Faculty of Agriculture (A.B.U) are oriented with longer sides facing the north and south

axis, and most of the fenestrations are on this axis with fewer on the east and west. In the case of Faculty of Agriculture (B.U.K), due to the irregular and oblique shape of the Faculty, it makes it difficult to achieve proper orientation. Some of the windows with no shading devices are directly exposed to sun rays. Most of the faculty component buildings are well oriented with respect to sun and wind directions with longer side facing north and south direction in School of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology (FUTM).

Form of the Building

The buildings within the Faculty of Agriculture (A.B.U) are rectangular in shape. This affects exposure to wind as well as sunshine accessibility. The shape

also limits its exposure on east and west sides, and consequently results for shallow floor plan that encourages natural cross ventilation. In the case of Faculty of Agriculture (B.U.K), the buildings are semi hexagonal in shape. It is also not a compact form as all the offices are spread

in single banking, thereby exposing most of the perimeter walls to sunshine. In the case of School of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology (FUTM). The building form is mostly rectangular which limit its exposure on east and west sides to the sun.

Table 2: Building Orientation and Form

	A.B.U Zaria	B.U.K	FUT Minna	Access System
Building Orientation	4	3	4	3.7
Building Form	4	3	5	4

Solar Shading

Faculty of Agriculture (A.B.U) buildings has a well-designed sun control and shading devices placed in the building's facade. These reduce the building peak heat gain and cooling requirements. There is also proper landscaping which provide shade and reduces heat gain, these trees also provide shade to the roofs, walls and windows.

In the case of Faculty of agriculture (B.U.K), the buildings do not have a well-designed sun control and shading

devices placed in the building's facade. There seems to be no deciduous trees around the site to provide additional shading. The design does not exhibit any attempt to shade the roof, which is the major receptor of solar radiation.

Use of fin shading devices on north and south facing walls; these reduce the building peak heat gain and cooling requirements presence of deciduous and non-deciduous trees within and outside the School of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology (FUTM).

Table 3: Solar Shading

	A.B.U Zaria	B.U.K	FUT Minna	Average Score
Solar Shading	4	2	3	3

- (a) Shading by overhangs, louvers and awnings
- (b) Shading by roof
- (c) Shading by trees and vegetation

Induced Ventilation

In Faculty of Agriculture (A.B.U), Operable windows are provided on the external walls; in case of double banking, high level windows were provided on the corridor walls. The window openings help to move hot air out, so a buoyancy effect can be created by the use of these openings. In the faculty building there is no solar chimney, air vent and wind towers which can enhance the ventilation of the buildings.

In the case of Faculty of Agriculture (B.U.K), the Faculty complex is generally

single banked which enables windows to be easily placed on the sides of positive and negative pressure for cross ventilation. In the Faculty building, there is no solar chimney, air vent and wind towers which can enhance the ventilation of the buildings.

It was observed that projectable windows on external walls and high level windows on internal walls were used in School of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology (FUTM). However, solar chimney, air vent and wind towers was not used in the Faculty building.

Table 4: Induced Ventilation

	A.B.U Zaria	B.U.K	FUT Minna	Average Score
Induced Ventilation	3	4	3	3.3
(a) Solar Chimney				
(b) Air Vent				
(c) Wind Tower				
(d) window openings				

Building Materials and Construction

The building materials used in all the cases studied are sanderete blocks, which has a characteristic of low thermal mass. This means that they have low time lag, or not capable of storing heat for a long time. The windows are made of single

glazing which also provide low insulation and most of the heat gain or loss is through the windows. The roofs are gently sloped and covered with corrugated long span aluminium roofing sheet as seen in Table 5.

Table 5: Building Materials and Construction

	A.B.U Zaria	B.U.K	FUT Minna	Average Score
Building Materials and construction	1	1	1	1

- (a) High thermal mass building materials
- (b) Double glazing
- (c) Cavity walls

Evaporative Cooling Techniques

There are no means for evaporative cooling such as a water body and passive

downdraft evaporative cooling tower within the three cases studied as presented in Table 6 below.

Table 6: Evaporative Cooling Techniques Source: Authors, 2017

	A.B.U Zaria	B.U.K	FUT Minna	Average Score
Evaporative cooling	0	0	0	0

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

From the analysis of the cases studied, it was observed that Building form and Orientation of the buildings are inter-related. The building forms are mostly rectangular which limit its exposure on east and west sides to the sun. Most of the buildings are well oriented with respect to sun and wind directions with longer side facing north and south direction in all the cases studied.

Solar Shading techniques were mainly applied in the Faculty of Agriculture A.B.U., this is due to the fact that shading devices on the windows and a well landscaped environment were used extensively. The least in score in terms of ranking of application of solar shading is the Faculty of Agriculture Bayero University Kano (B.U.K) which has little or no shading devices on the windows, and there are no deciduous trees around the sites to provide additional shading. The analysis of materials used in the construction of the buildings studied indicated that, sandcrete blocks were mainly used for both cladding and partitioning of spaces. Studies have shown the sandcrete blocks have low thermal massing which prevents it from retaining heat for a long duration (Saliu

and Achimugu, 2016). Furthermore, the windows were made of single glazing which are characterized with low insulation. This has a negative effect on both heat gain or loss in the buildings. Based on the above analysis, materials that can enhance passive architecture were not utilized in the cases studied.

Induced ventilation technique was also poorly applied in all the cases. All the cases do not have wind towers, air vents and solar chimneys, which aid in providing induced ventilation. The only means of natural ventilation applied in the cases studied are windows openings. Evaporative Cooling Techniques are also completely absent in all the three cases studied. There are no means for evaporative cooling such as a water body and passive downdraft evaporative cooling tower.

CONCLUSION

Passive architecture seeks to provide minimal use of mechanical means of energy in building. This paper has highlighted the principles of passive architecture and examined the extent of its application in design of Faculties of Agricultural buildings in selected institutions in Nigeria (Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Bayero University Kano

and Federal University of Technology Minna).

It concludes that most of the cases studied, extensively applied some of the principle of passive architecture in the design of their various buildings. These includes: Building orientation, Building form and Solar shading with an average mean score of 3.67. This could be attributed to the fact that these three principles are considered as default in all architectural design and emphases are laid on them in the training of professionals. However, analysis of other principle's (Induced ventilation, Evaporative cooling, Materials and construction) application in the cases studied had an average mean score of 1.43. The implication of this is that the principles were little or not applied in the faculty buildings studied.

It is recommended that with the growing interest in passive architecture in the tropical regions, application of all the principles is very paramount to achieve passively designed and built buildings in Nigeria. Furthermore, emphasis should be made on the process and application of techniques such as: Evaporative cooling, Induced ventilation and selection of appropriate materials for construction as well as training of Architects and other professionals in the building industry.

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